

THE INTERACTION OF IODINE AND STARCH

PART II. IODIDE IONS IN THE COMPLEX

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Determinations have been made of the iodide ion contents of starch and amylose-iodine complexes, precipitated in the presence of various concentrations of potassium iodide. The ratio of iodide ions to iodine increases with concentration of potassium iodide employed but this increase is more marked in the amylose-iodine complex. The maximum value of the ratio, found for amylose-iodine complex, corresponds to that required for the formation of the triiodide ion. Prolonged washing of the complex leads to a partial removal of both iodine and iodide ions.

Baldwin, Bear and Rundle (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 111) state that iodide ions can enter the starch-iodine complex and that these displace some of the iodine molecules, thereby increasing the starch-iodine ratio in the complex. It has, however, been shown in Part I of this series (Mukherjee and Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 121) that the starch-iodine ratio of the precipitated iodine complexes of starch or amylose remains independent of the concentration of potassium iodide in the reaction mixture at the time of precipitation and also remains practically unchanged on subsequent washing with solutions of salts like sodium chloride or sulphate. In view of these observations, it was considered to be of interest to make a quantitative study of the proportions of iodide ions present in the complex under different conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The starch or amylose complexes were precipitated in the manner described in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The iodide content of the complex was obtained by taking the difference between the total and free iodine contents. For the estimation of total iodine, the precipitated complex was oxidised with a mixture of potassium dichromate and sulphuric acid and the iodine was distilled off and absorbed in hot dilute sodium hydroxide solution from which it was again liberated by acidification and was titrated with standard thiosulphate solution. An all-glass apparatus, specially designed in this laboratory and described earlier by Basu and Goswami (*Science & Culture*, 1938, 4, 299), was used for this purpose.

The determination of the free iodine in the complex by titration with sodium thiosulphate, prior to the estimation of total iodine by the above method, led to erratic results in the latter estimation. In order to obviate this difficulty, the free iodine content was calculated indirectly by using the constant ratio of starch to iodine found in separate experiments.

The accuracy of the distillation method, where this disturbing factor was absent, was found to be within $\pm 1.0\%$, and it was verified by control experiments that the presence of starch did not introduce any significant error.

The data obtained for potato starch and for amylose isolated from the same starch are given respectively in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
Iodide content of potato starch-iodine complex

Starch taken.	Conc. of KI.	Iodine content of Free (a)	Iodine content of the complex Total (b)	Iodide content. (b - a)	Iodide/Iodine ratio $\left(\frac{b-a}{a}\right)$	Remarks
0.8281 g.	1.210 M	0.1270 g.	0.1887 g.	0.0417 g.	0.329	Pptd. complex washed 6 times with 10% Na ₂ SO ₄
0.4076	0.530	0.0815	0.1003	0.0188	0.231	
0.4508	0.176	0.0912	0.1064	0.0152	0.167	
0.3913	0.046	0.0782	0.0891	0.0099	0.125	
0.5403	1.210	0.0860	0.1111	0.0251	0.292	

TABLE II

Iodide content of amylose-iodine complex

Amylose taken.	Conc. of K I.	Iodine content of Free (a)	Iodine content of the complex Total (b)	Iodide content of complex (b - a)	Iodide/Iodine ratio $\left(\frac{b-a}{a}\right)$
0.3914 g.	1.21 M	0.0799 g.	0.1178 g.	0.0379 g.	0.474
0.3167	0.530	0.0646	0.0861	0.0205	0.318
0.3511	0.176	0.0741	0.0944	0.0203	0.274
0.3333	0.046	0.0680	0.0776	0.0096	0.141

DISCUSSION

The results given in Tables I and II show that the starch-iodine complex generally contains iodide ions, the proportion of which varies with the concentration of potassium iodide in the solution from which complex is precipitated. For a variation of the concentration of potassium iodide from 0.046M to 1.210M, the ratio of iodide ions to free iodine in the complex varies from 0.125 to 0.329 for potato starch and from 0.141 to 0.470 for amylose. It is significant that the maximum value of this ratio found for amylose approaches 0.50 which is the proportion required for the formation of the triiodide ion.

The fact that the ratios of iodide to free iodine are systematically lower for potato starch than for amylose indicates that iodide ions enter into the non-amylose portion of the unfractionated starch with less facility than into amylose as present in the complex.

One sample of the precipitated starch-iodine complex was subjected to prolonged washing with 10% sodium sulphate solution in order to see if the iodide ions were removable by washing. This had the effect of raising the starch-iodine ratio from about 3.90 to 4.90, and of reducing the ratio of iodide to free iodine from 0.329 to 0.292. The relatively small change in the latter ratio indicates that both iodide ions and iodine molecules are removed simultaneously during prolonged washing. Further work on these lines is in progress.

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